

Data for the Structural Dynamic, Aerodynamic, and Propulsive Models of the GNBA

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This document contains data for the structural dynamic, the aerodynamic, and the propulsive models of the GNBA (Generic Narrow-Body Airliner). The geometric, inertia, and rigidity properties of the twenty beams that constitute the structural dynamic model are available in a form suitable for a model based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method, but could be adapted for beam finite elements as well. Inertia properties of hundreds of lumped masses are also provided for two different mass configurations of the aircraft: one with the operating empty weight and the other with the design weight. The lumped masses refer to nonstructural items of the aircraft, like the engines, crew, payload, and fuel, among many others. Lastly, important geometric, aerodynamic, and propulsive data are detailed for the cruise configuration of the aircraft, with flaps and landing gears up.

I. Introduction

Studying the flight dynamics of a flexible aircraft requires several different kinds of numerical models. The structural dynamic model includes the stiffness and inertia properties of the complete airframe. Several items are unimportant in terms of stiffness, e.g., payload and fuel, but have significant inertia properties. They must also be considered in the structural dynamic model. Moreover, the aerodynamic model must be capable of dealing with rigid-body and aeroelastic motions, as well as with the deflection of control surfaces. Knowing in detail the aircraft geometry is thus indispensable for the calculation of aerodynamic loads. A propulsive model that allows calculating the forces and moments caused by the engines is also fundamental.

In this document, data are provided for the structural dynamic, the aerodynamic, and the propulsive models of the GNBA (Generic Narrow-Body Airliner). The GNBA, originally developed by the author in Ref. [1], intends to resemble real-world aircraft of the same category, like the Boeing 737, the Airbus A320 and A220, and the Embraer E-Jet family. It is a conventional aircraft, with under-wing-mounted engines, conventional tail planes, and seating capacity for 130 passengers, five-abreast. The design point is Mach 0.78 at an altitude of 11582 m. The maximum take-off weight (MTOW) is 64200 kgf. The isometric and the three orthogonal views of the GNBA are shown in Fig. 1.

The rest of this document is organized as follows. In Sec. II, the geometric, inertia, and rigidity properties of the

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Fig. 1 The GNBA isometric, top, side, and front views.

twenty beams that constitute the structural dynamic model of the GNBA are provided. Then, in Sec. III, the inertia properties of nonstructural items are listed for two different mass configurations of the aircraft: one corresponding to the operating empty weight (OEW) and the other corresponding to the design weight (DW). Section IV contains a description of the most important geometric properties for the aerodynamic model of the GNBA, which considers the cruise configuration, with flaps and landing gears up. Lastly, Section V lists the data necessary for the propulsive model of the aircraft.

II. Data for the Structural Dynamic Model

In Ref. [1], the GNBA was modeled using beam finite elements. However, to allow a simpler implementation using the Rayleigh-Ritz method, the rigidity and inertia properties have been fitted with polynomials.

The proposed GNBA structure comprises 20 beams, as depicted in Fig. 2. The point S lies where the wing beams are connected to the fuselage. It has the coordinates:

$$x_S = 16.498 \text{ m}$$

$$y_S = z_S = 0$$

in the same coordinate system adopted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2 The twenty beams of the structural dynamic model of the GNBA.

A basic coordinate system is considered that is given the subscript 0. This basic coordinate system $Sx_0y_0z_0$ has its axes parallel to those of Fig. 1, but with the origin at S . The i th beam has a local coordinate system with the symbol i in which the axis y_i is along the length of the beam.

The geometric and the connectivity properties of the beams of the GNBA structural dynamic model are listed in Table 1. All interconnections are such that, for the j th beam connected to the i th beam, the connection point in the i th

beam corresponds to the lengthwise coordinate y_i given in the fourth column of the table, whereas the same point in the j th beam is always given by $y_j = 0$.

The transformation matrix $\mathbf{C}_{i/0}$ from the basic coordinate system 0 to the i th beam coordinate system is calculated with the equation:

$$\mathbf{C}_{i/0} = (1 - \cos \mu)\mathbf{nn}^T + \cos \mu \mathbf{I}_3 - \sin \mu \tilde{\mathbf{n}} \quad (1)$$

where the rotation vectors (column matrices) $\mathbf{n}$ and rotation angles μ are provided in the fifth and last columns of Table 1, respectively. In Eq. (1), the angle μ is in radians, $\mathbf{I}_3$ is the identity matrix of size 3, and the skew-symmetric operator is defined by the equation:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{n}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{e}_{3,3}^T \mathbf{n} & \mathbf{e}_{3,2}^T \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{e}_{3,3}^T \mathbf{n} & 0 & -\mathbf{e}_{3,1}^T \mathbf{n} \\ -\mathbf{e}_{3,2}^T \mathbf{n} & \mathbf{e}_{3,1}^T \mathbf{n} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_{3,i}$ is the i th column of $\mathbf{I}_3$.

The polynomials for the bending and torsional rigidities $(EI_{xx})_i$, $(EI_{zz})_i$, $(EI_{xz})_i$, and $(GJ)_i$ of the 20 beams are given in Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

The structural mass of the aircraft is modeled with distributed properties of mass per unit length, $m_i(y_i)$; moment of inertia about y_i per unit length, $\mathcal{I}_{yy,i}(y_i)$; and cross-sectional center of mass location, $x_{C,i}(y_i)$, along the beams. These properties are listed in Tables 6 and 7. Moreover, for all the GNBA beams, $z_{C,i}(y_i) = 0$, $\mathcal{I}_{xx,i}(y_i) = 0$, $\mathcal{I}_{zz,i}(y_i) = 0$, and $\mathcal{I}_{xz,i}(y_i) = 0$.

Table 1 The twenty beams of the GNBA structural dynamic model.

Beam	Component	Length L_i [m]	Connects to beam	$\mathbf{n}^T$	μ [deg]
1	Fuselage	8.998	–	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	90
2	Fuselage	7.556	1, at $y_1 = L_1$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0609 & -0.0609 & 0.9963 \end{bmatrix}$	90.213
3	Fuselage	13.502	1, at $y_1 = 0$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$	90
4	Fuselage	9.200	3, at $y_3 = L_3$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0518 & -0.0518 & -0.9973 \end{bmatrix}$	90.154
5	Right wing	2.169	1, at $y_1 = 0$	$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	31.473
6	Right wing	4.215	5, at $y_5 = L_5$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.2866 & -0.0625 & -0.9560 \end{bmatrix}$	25.678
7	Right wing	7.809	6, at $y_6 = L_6$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1142 & -0.0277 & -0.9931 \end{bmatrix}$	27.395
8	Right wing	4.273	7, at $y_7 = L_7$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1142 & -0.0277 & -0.9931 \end{bmatrix}$	27.395
9	Right engine pylon	2.923	6, at $y_6 = 3.550$ m	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0094 & -0.0094 & 0.9999 \end{bmatrix}$	90.005
10	Right horizontal tail	0.663	4, at $y_4 = 6.517$ m	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	27.777
11	Right horizontal tail	5.891	10, at $y_{10} = L_{10}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.2355 & -0.0536 & -0.9704 \end{bmatrix}$	26.378
12	Vertical tail	1.100	4, at $y_4 = 4.807$ m	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	90
13	Vertical tail	6.854	12, at $y_{12} = L_{12}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.9328 & 0.2549 & -0.2549 \end{bmatrix}$	93.983
14	Left wing	2.169	1, at $y_1 = 0$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.2712 & -0.9625 \end{bmatrix}$	180
15	Left wing	4.215	14, at $y_{14} = L_{14}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0142 & -0.0652 & -0.9978 \end{bmatrix}$	155.470
16	Left wing	7.809	15, at $y_{15} = L_{15}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0067 & -0.0278 & -0.9996 \end{bmatrix}$	152.799
17	Left wing	4.273	16, at $y_{16} = L_{16}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0067 & -0.0278 & -0.9996 \end{bmatrix}$	152.799
18	Left engine pylon	2.923	15, at $y_{15} = 3.550$ m	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0094 & -0.0094 & 0.9999 \end{bmatrix}$	90.005
19	Left horizontal tail	0.663	4, at $y_4 = 6.517$ m	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -0.2400 & -0.9708 \end{bmatrix}$	180
20	Left horizontal tail	5.891	19, at $y_{19} = L_{19}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0125 & -0.0551 & -0.9984 \end{bmatrix}$	154.417

Table 2 The bending rigidity of each beam about the local axis x_i , in SI units.

Beam	$(EI_{xx})_i = (EI_{xx})_{3,i}y_i^3 + (EI_{xx})_{2,i}y_i^2 + (EI_{xx})_{1,i}y_i + (EI_{xx})_{0,i}$			
	$(EI_{xx})_{3,i}$	$(EI_{xx})_{2,i}$	$(EI_{xx})_{1,i}$	$(EI_{xx})_{0,i}$
1	4.0713×10^5	2.7246×10^7	-5.4388×10^8	4.6161×10^9
2	5.2314×10^6	-9.3336×10^7	2.6423×10^8	1.7111×10^9
3	2.8591×10^6	-7.5529×10^7	3.5952×10^8	4.1751×10^9
4	-6.5639×10^5	1.7469×10^7	-3.3124×10^8	2.3348×10^9
5 and 14	0	0	0	5.9335×10^8
6 and 15	9.3745×10^6	-8.0416×10^7	1.3319×10^8	2.7572×10^8
7 and 16	-1.7244×10^4	1.0998×10^6	-1.9148×10^7	1.0459×10^8
8 and 17	-1.7244×10^4	6.9582×10^5	-5.1260×10^6	1.3918×10^7
9 and 18	0	0	0	1.1808×10^8
10 and 19	0	0	0	1.8155×10^8
11 and 20	5.0889×10^4	1.0449×10^5	-5.9072×10^6	2.1972×10^7
12	0	0	0	2.2140×10^8
13	3.2967×10^5	-2.0025×10^6	-1.3518×10^7	8.6089×10^7

Table 3 The bending rigidity of each beam about the local axis z_i , in SI units.

Beam	$(EI_{zz})_i = (EI_{zz})_{3,i}y_i^3 + (EI_{zz})_{2,i}y_i^2 + (EI_{zz})_{1,i}y_i + (EI_{zz})_{0,i}$			
	$(EI_{zz})_{3,i}$	$(EI_{zz})_{2,i}$	$(EI_{zz})_{1,i}$	$(EI_{zz})_{0,i}$
1	4.0713×10^5	2.7246×10^7	-5.4388×10^8	4.6161×10^9
2	5.2314×10^6	-9.3336×10^7	2.6423×10^8	1.7111×10^9
3	2.8591×10^6	-7.5529×10^7	3.5952×10^8	4.1751×10^9
4	-6.5639×10^5	1.7469×10^7	-3.3124×10^8	2.3348×10^9
5 and 14	0	0	0	7.3948×10^9
6 and 15	1.2246×10^8	-8.3127×10^8	-2.6448×10^8	1.0353×10^{10}
7 and 16	-3.8931×10^5	3.5825×10^7	-6.5583×10^8	3.4505×10^9
8 and 17	-3.8931×10^5	2.6705×10^7	-1.6754×10^8	3.2836×10^8
9 and 18	0	0	0	2.9520×10^7
10 and 19	0	0	0	7.5276×10^8
11 and 20	4.6253×10^5	1.2967×10^6	-5.7525×10^7	2.1058×10^8
12	0	0	0	9.0036×10^8
13	1.9973×10^6	-1.1897×10^7	-8.6636×10^7	5.4543×10^8

Table 4 The cross-coupled bending rigidity of each beam about the local axes x_i and z_i , in SI units.

Beam	$(EI_{xz})_i = (EI_{xz})_{3,i}y_i^3 + (EI_{xz})_{2,i}y_i^2 + (EI_{xz})_{1,i}y_i + (EI_{xz})_{0,i}$			
	$(EI_{xz})_{3,i}$	$(EI_{xz})_{2,i}$	$(EI_{xz})_{1,i}$	$(EI_{xz})_{0,i}$
5	0	0	0	-8.6346×10^7
6	4.4406×10^5	-2.4966×10^6	-1.4132×10^7	7.2349×10^7
7	-4.0222×10^{-1}	1.6289×10^1	-8.3242×10^2	3.3029×10^3
8	-4.0222×10^{-1}	6.8662	-6.5160×10^2	-2.3957×10^3
14	0	0	0	8.6346×10^7
15	-4.4406×10^5	2.4966×10^6	1.4132×10^7	-7.2349×10^7
16	4.0222×10^{-1}	-1.6289×10^1	8.3242×10^2	-3.3029×10^3
17	4.0222×10^{-1}	-6.8662	6.5160×10^2	2.3957×10^3
All others	0	0	0	0

Table 5 The torsional rigidity of each beam about the local axis y_i , in SI units.

Beam	$(GJ)_i = (GJ)_{3,i}y_i^3 + (GJ)_{2,i}y_i^2 + (GJ)_{1,i}y_i + (GJ)_{0,i}$			
	$(GJ)_{3,i}$	$(GJ)_{2,i}$	$(GJ)_{1,i}$	$(GJ)_{0,i}$
1	-1.0213×10^6	3.2050×10^7	-3.8312×10^8	3.2157×10^9
2	7.0843×10^6	-1.0771×10^8	2.8793×10^8	1.2378×10^9
3	1.7864×10^6	-4.7808×10^7	2.2951×10^8	2.9386×10^9
4	8.5115×10^5	-1.7510×10^6	-2.3963×10^8	1.7721×10^9
5 and 14	0	0	0	6.1592×10^8
6 and 15	5.2701×10^6	-2.0123×10^7	-1.8492×10^8	8.5670×10^8
7 and 16	-2.5411×10^4	1.1180×10^6	-1.8470×10^7	1.0549×10^8
8 and 17	-2.5411×10^4	5.2270×10^5	-5.6578×10^6	1.7333×10^7
9 and 18	0	0	0	1.9421×10^8
10 and 19	0	0	0	8.6340×10^6
11 and 20	4.4119×10^4	1.1749×10^5	-5.4172×10^6	1.9873×10^7
12	0	0	0	1.1764×10^8
13	2.7177×10^5	-1.6304×10^6	-1.1606×10^7	7.3522×10^7

Table 6 The mass and the moment of inertia per unit length of each beam, in SI units.

Beam	$\mathbf{m}_i = \mathbf{m}_{1,i}y_i + \mathbf{m}_{0,i}$		$\mathcal{I}_{yy,i} = \mathcal{I}_{yy,3,i}y_i^3 + \mathcal{I}_{yy,2,i}y_i^2 + \mathcal{I}_{yy,1,i}y_i + \mathcal{I}_{yy,0,i}$			
	$\mathbf{m}_{0,i}$	$\mathbf{m}_{1,i}$	$\mathcal{I}_{yy,0,i}$	$\mathcal{I}_{yy,1,i}$	$\mathcal{I}_{yy,2,i}$	$\mathcal{I}_{yy,3,i}$
1	252.40	0	348.2	0	0	0
2	384.98	-33.557	518.94	-60.893	0	0
3	270.10	0	431.26	0	0	0
4	353.93	-18.906	454.92	-22.356	0	0
5 and 14	276.70	0	299.34	0	0	0
6 and 15	502.15	-53.853	757.18	-206.71	16.549	-0.57392
7 and 16	272.40	-18.081	125.41	-16.711	0.70338	-0.012551
8 and 17	129.24	-16.903	31.737	-8.0221	0.40935	-0.012551
11 and 20	106.27	-16.480	44.084	-12.846	1.2395	-0.052125
13	111.33	-13.002	93.330	-22.071	1.5664	-0.047934
All others	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7 The cross-sectional center of mass location of each beam, in SI units.

Beam	$x_{C,i} = \frac{N_{x,C,0,i} + N_{x,C,1,i}y_i + N_{x,C,2,i}y_i^2}{\mathbf{m}_i}$		
	$N_{x,C,0,i}$	$N_{x,C,1,i}$	$N_{x,C,2,i}$
6	51.642	-16.346	0.96214
7	2.6907	-1.1483	0.050481
8	-3.1978	-0.35992	0.050481
11	3.3981	-0.98886	0.071905
13	13.727	-2.3224	0.097788
15	-51.642	16.346	-0.96214
16	-2.6907	1.1483	-0.050481
17	3.1978	0.35992	-0.050481
20	-3.3981	0.98886	-0.071905
All others	0	0	0

III. Inertia Properties of Nonstructural Items

The GNBA can have different distributions of payload and fuel mass in the fuselage and in the wing. Each different distribution of mass is named a “mass configuration” of the vehicle.

One possible mass configuration is that with the *operating empty weight* (OEW), which includes everything that is basically needed for operation, including the crew but only the unusable fuel.

Another possible configuration is that with the *design weight* (DW), including all the masses of the OEW configuration in addition to 13000 kg of payload (passengers, luggage, and cargo) and 6665 kg of fuel.

Whereas the structural masses and moments of inertia can be adequately included using beam mass properties per unit length, the nonstructural masses are included in the structural dynamic model using lumped masses. The j th lumped mass has its center of mass M_j rigidly connected to a point K_j of a beam. In this document, the relative position vector from K_j to M_j is given by $s_{KM,j,0}$ and written in the basic coordinate system 0 of the structural dynamic model. The lumped mass has the mass m_j and the inertia matrix $\mathbf{J}_{j,0}$ about its center of mass and with respect to the directions of the axes of the basic coordinate system. The inertia matrix can be written as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{j,0} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx,j,0} & -I_{xy,j,0} & -I_{xz,j,0} \\ -I_{xy,j,0} & I_{yy,j,0} & -I_{yz,j,0} \\ -I_{xz,j,0} & -I_{yz,j,0} & I_{zz,j,0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Because of their almost negligible contributions to the aircraft inertia matrix, the lumped masses’ products of inertia are assumed null, i.e., $I_{xy,j,0} = I_{xz,j,0} = I_{yz,j,0} = 0$ for all lumped masses.

The relative position vector can be written as:

$$\mathbf{s}_{KM,j,0} = \begin{bmatrix} s_{KM,j,x,0} & s_{KM,j,y,0} & s_{KM,j,z,0} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (4)$$

The j th lumped mass is rigidly connected to the i th beam of the structural dynamic model at a point K_j on the beam elastic axis. The point K_j is given by the coordinate y_i in the i th beam local coordinate system.

It is then possible to specify the properties of the lumped masses as in Table 8, which corresponds to the OEW mass configuration. The beams and the lumped masses of this mass configuration are shown in Fig. 3.

Table 8 The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
1	8	2.357	0.616	0	0.118	24.76	0	0	0
2	6	3.494	1.001	0	0.159	49.52	0	0	0
3	7	2.646	-1.005	0	0.118	43.33	0	0	0
4	6	1.941	2.041	0	0.211	37.14	0	0	0
5	7	3.772	0.881	0	0.105	49.52	0	0	0
6	6	1.941	1.541	0	0.211	150.11	0	0	0
7	7	1.383	0.572	0	0.088	121.20	0	0	0
8	7	5.626	0.335	0	0.082	121.20	0	0	0
9	2	6.549	0	0	0.041	43.47	0	0	0
10	4	3.821	0	0	0.085	114.28	0	0	0
11	4	7.792	0	0	0.093	161.93	0	0	0
12	2	2.519	0	0	0.307	225.07	0	0	0
13	4	2.011	0	0	0.092	225.07	0	0	0
14	4	1.207	0	0	0.075	172.27	0	0	0
15	2	1.511	0	0	0.384	338.15	0	0	0
16	4	3.770	0	0	0.010	338.15	0	0	0
17	1	0.498	0	0	-1.200	19.79	0	0	0
18	2	0.504	0	0	-0.439	370.40	0	0	0
19	1	1.498	0	0	-0.500	76.20	0	0	0
20	2	4.534	0	0	0.352	370.61	0	0	0
21	2	4.030	0	0	0.291	855.70	267.84	0	186.00
22	2	5.541	0	0	0.275	101.75	0	0	0
23	3	0.272	0	-0.800	-1.200	310.00	0	0	0

Table 8 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
24	3	0.272	0	0.800	-1.200	310.00	0	0	0
25	1	7.298	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
26	1	6.485	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
27	1	5.672	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
28	1	4.859	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
29	1	4.046	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
30	1	3.234	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
31	1	2.421	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
32	1	1.608	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
33	1	0.795	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
34	3	0.018	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
35	3	1.288	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
36	3	2.100	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
37	3	2.913	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
38	3	3.726	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
39	3	4.539	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
40	3	5.352	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
41	3	6.164	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
42	3	6.977	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
43	3	7.790	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
44	3	8.603	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
45	3	9.416	0	-1.049	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
46	3	10.228	0	-1.029	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0

Table 8 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
47	3	11.041	0	-1.009	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
48	3	11.854	0	-0.989	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
49	3	12.667	0	-0.969	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
50	3	13.480	0	-0.949	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
51	1	7.298	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
52	1	6.485	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
53	1	5.672	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
54	1	4.859	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
55	1	4.046	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
56	1	3.234	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
57	1	2.421	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
58	1	1.608	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
59	1	0.795	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
60	3	0.018	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
61	3	1.288	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
62	3	2.100	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
63	3	2.913	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
64	3	3.726	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
65	3	4.539	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
66	3	5.352	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
67	3	6.164	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
68	3	6.977	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
69	3	7.790	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0

Table 8 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
70	3	8.603	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
71	3	9.416	0	0.767	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
72	3	10.228	0	0.747	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
73	3	11.041	0	0.727	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
74	3	11.854	0	0.707	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
75	3	12.667	0	0.687	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
76	3	13.480	0	0.667	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
77	11	2.618	0.601	0	0	61.90	0	0	0
78	13	3.808	0.756	0	0	49.52	0	0	0
79	9	2.923	-1.391	0	-1.270	143.60	144.80	228.20	228.20
80	9	2.923	-0.233	0	-1.359	2830.00	400.10	2379.00	2379.00
81	9	2.923	0.053	0	0	448.90	18.70	920.00	920.00
82	6	0	2.742	-0.950	0.084	408.00	28.10	28.10	50.00
83	6	0.166	2.423	0	0.147	508.00	173.00	7.62	173.00
84	6	1.830	1.587	0	0.047	103.00	3.51	6.85	7.62
85	2	4.030	0	0	-1.009	136.00	5.88	10.90	5.88
86	2	3.325	0	0	-1.095	174.00	1.81	33.50	33.50
87	2	2.519	0	0	-1.193	38.30	1.02	1.02	1.02
88	17	2.357	0.616	0	0.118	24.76	0	0	0
89	15	3.494	1.001	0	0.159	49.52	0	0	0
90	16	2.646	-1.005	0	0.118	43.33	0	0	0
91	15	1.941	2.041	0	0.211	37.14	0	0	0
92	16	3.772	0.881	0	0.105	49.52	0	0	0

Table 8 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
93	15	1.941	1.541	0	0.211	150.11	0	0	0
94	16	1.383	0.572	0	0.088	121.20	0	0	0
95	16	5.626	0.335	0	0.082	121.20	0	0	0
96	20	2.618	0.601	0	0	61.90	0	0	0
97	18	2.923	-1.391	0	-1.270	143.60	144.80	228.20	228.20
98	18	2.923	-0.233	0	-1.359	2830.00	400.10	2379.00	2379.00
99	18	2.923	0.053	0	0	448.90	18.70	920.00	920.00
100	15	0	2.742	0.950	0.084	408.00	28.10	28.10	50.00
101	15	0.166	2.423	0	0.147	508.00	173.00	7.62	173.00
102	15	1.830	1.587	0	0.047	103.00	3.51	6.85	7.62

In addition to the lumped masses listed in Table 8, the DW mass configuration also has payload and fuel lumped masses. The payload mass distribution is listed in Table 9, whereas the fuel mass distribution is listed in Table 10. The beams and the lumped masses of this mass configuration are depicted in Fig. 4.

Table 9 The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
103	1	7.298	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
104	1	7.298	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
105	1	7.298	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
106	1	7.298	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
107	1	7.298	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
108	1	6.485	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
109	1	6.485	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
110	1	6.485	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
111	1	6.485	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
112	1	6.485	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
113	1	5.672	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
114	1	5.672	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
115	1	5.672	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
116	1	5.672	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
117	1	5.672	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
118	1	4.859	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
119	1	4.859	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
120	1	4.859	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
121	1	4.859	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
122	1	4.859	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
123	1	4.046	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
124	1	4.046	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
125	1	4.046	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
126	1	4.046	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
127	1	4.046	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
128	1	3.234	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
129	1	3.234	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
130	1	3.234	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
131	1	3.234	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
132	1	3.234	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
133	1	2.421	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
134	1	2.421	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
135	1	2.421	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
136	1	2.421	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
137	1	2.421	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
138	1	1.608	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
139	1	1.608	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
140	1	1.608	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
141	1	1.608	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
142	1	1.608	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
143	1	0.795	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
144	1	0.795	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
145	1	0.795	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
146	1	0.795	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
147	1	0.795	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
148	3	0.018	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
149	3	0.018	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
150	3	0.018	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
151	3	0.018	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
152	3	0.018	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
153	3	1.288	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
154	3	1.288	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
155	3	1.288	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
156	3	1.288	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
157	3	1.288	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
158	3	2.100	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
159	3	2.100	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
160	3	2.100	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
161	3	2.100	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
162	3	2.100	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
163	3	2.913	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
164	3	2.913	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
165	3	2.913	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
166	3	2.913	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
167	3	2.913	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
168	3	3.726	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
169	3	3.726	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
170	3	3.726	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
171	3	3.726	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
172	3	3.726	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
173	3	4.539	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
174	3	4.539	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
175	3	4.539	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
176	3	4.539	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
177	3	4.539	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
178	3	5.352	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
179	3	5.352	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
180	3	5.352	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
181	3	5.352	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
182	3	5.352	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
183	3	6.164	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
184	3	6.164	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
185	3	6.164	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
186	3	6.164	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
187	3	6.164	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
188	3	6.977	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
189	3	6.977	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
190	3	6.977	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
191	3	6.977	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
192	3	6.977	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
193	3	7.790	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
194	3	7.790	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
195	3	7.790	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
196	3	7.790	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
197	3	7.790	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
198	3	8.603	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
199	3	8.603	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
200	3	8.603	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
201	3	8.603	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
202	3	8.603	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
203	3	9.416	0.000	-1.330	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
204	3	9.416	0.000	-0.767	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
205	3	9.416	0.000	0.205	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
206	3	9.416	0.000	0.767	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
207	3	9.416	0.000	1.330	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
208	3	10.228	0.000	-1.310	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
209	3	10.228	0.000	-0.747	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
210	3	10.228	0.000	0.185	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
211	3	10.228	0.000	0.747	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
212	3	10.228	0.000	1.310	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
213	3	11.041	0.000	-1.290	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
214	3	11.041	0.000	-0.727	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
215	3	11.041	0.000	0.165	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
216	3	11.041	0.000	0.727	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
217	3	11.041	0.000	1.290	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
218	3	11.854	0.000	-1.270	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
219	3	11.854	0.000	-0.707	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
220	3	11.854	0.000	0.145	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
221	3	11.854	0.000	0.707	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
222	3	11.854	0.000	1.270	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
223	3	12.667	0.000	-1.250	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
224	3	12.667	0.000	-0.687	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
225	3	12.667	0.000	0.125	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
226	3	12.667	0.000	0.687	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
227	3	12.667	0.000	1.250	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
228	3	13.480	0.000	-1.230	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
229	3	13.480	0.000	-0.667	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
230	3	13.480	0.000	0.105	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
231	3	13.480	0.000	0.667	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
232	3	13.480	0.000	1.230	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
233	1	7.298	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
234	1	6.485	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
235	1	5.672	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
236	1	4.859	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
237	1	4.046	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
238	1	3.234	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
239	1	2.421	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
240	1	1.608	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
241	1	0.795	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
242	3	0.018	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
243	3	1.288	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
244	3	2.100	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
245	3	2.913	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
246	3	3.726	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
247	3	4.539	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
248	3	5.352	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
249	3	6.164	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
250	3	6.977	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
251	3	7.790	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
252	3	8.603	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
253	3	9.416	0.000	-0.767	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
254	3	10.228	0.000	-0.747	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
255	3	11.041	0.000	-0.727	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
256	3	11.854	0.000	-0.707	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
257	3	12.667	0.000	-0.687	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
258	3	13.480	0.000	-0.667	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
259	1	7.298	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
260	1	6.485	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
261	1	5.672	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
262	1	4.859	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
263	1	4.046	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
264	1	3.234	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
265	1	2.421	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
266	1	1.608	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
267	1	0.795	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
268	3	0.018	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
269	3	1.288	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
270	3	2.100	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
271	3	2.913	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
272	3	3.726	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
273	3	4.539	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
274	3	5.352	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
275	3	6.164	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
276	3	6.977	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
277	3	7.790	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
278	3	8.603	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
279	3	9.416	0.000	0.767	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
280	3	10.228	0.000	0.747	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
281	3	11.041	0.000	0.727	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
282	3	11.854	0.000	0.707	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
283	3	12.667	0.000	0.687	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
284	3	13.480	0.000	0.667	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
285	1	7.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
286	1	6.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
287	1	5.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
288	1	4.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
289	1	3.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
290	3	4.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30

Table 9 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
291	3	5.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30
292	3	6.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30

Table 10 The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
293	5	0.271	0.077	0.000	-1.161	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
294	5	0.814	0.077	0.000	-0.878	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
295	5	1.356	0.077	0.000	-0.595	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
296	5	1.898	0.077	0.000	-0.312	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
297	6	0.051	0.077	0.000	-0.172	143.22	4.22	84.56	80.64
298	6	0.204	0.077	0.000	-0.177	134.30	3.58	77.05	73.75
299	6	0.358	0.077	0.000	-0.182	125.06	3.02	69.98	67.23
300	6	0.511	0.077	0.000	-0.187	116.99	2.52	63.32	61.06
301	6	0.664	0.077	0.000	-0.192	108.61	2.08	57.07	55.22
302	6	0.817	0.078	0.000	-0.198	100.40	1.70	51.21	49.72
303	6	0.970	0.078	0.000	-0.203	92.37	1.37	45.71	44.54
304	6	1.124	0.079	0.000	-0.208	84.52	1.09	40.57	39.66
305	6	1.277	0.080	0.000	-0.213	76.85	0.86	35.77	35.07
306	6	1.430	0.081	0.000	-0.218	69.36	0.66	31.29	30.77
307	6	1.583	0.082	0.000	-0.223	62.04	0.50	27.11	26.75

Table 10 (Continued) The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
308	6	1.736	0.084	0.000	-0.228	54.90	0.36	23.24	22.99
309	6	1.890	0.087	0.000	-0.233	47.95	0.26	19.64	19.48
310	6	2.043	0.090	0.000	-0.239	41.17	0.18	16.31	16.21
311	6	2.196	0.095	0.000	-0.244	34.57	0.12	13.23	13.18
312	6	2.349	0.103	0.000	-0.249	28.15	0.08	10.39	10.37
313	6	2.503	0.114	0.000	-0.255	21.90	0.05	7.77	7.77
314	6	2.656	0.135	0.000	-0.261	15.84	0.03	5.36	5.37
315	6	2.809	0.162	0.000	-0.267	10.10	0.01	3.22	3.23
316	6	2.962	0.169	0.000	-0.274	4.93	0.01	1.51	1.51
317	6	3.115	0.131	0.000	-0.281	0.98	0.00	0.30	0.30
318	14	0.271	-0.077	0.000	-1.161	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
319	14	0.814	-0.077	0.000	-0.878	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
320	14	1.356	-0.077	0.000	-0.595	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
321	14	1.898	-0.077	0.000	-0.312	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
322	15	0.051	-0.077	0.000	-0.172	143.22	4.22	84.56	80.64
323	15	0.204	-0.077	0.000	-0.177	134.30	3.58	77.05	73.75
324	15	0.358	-0.077	0.000	-0.182	125.06	3.02	69.98	67.23
325	15	0.511	-0.077	0.000	-0.187	116.99	2.52	63.32	61.06
326	15	0.664	-0.077	0.000	-0.192	108.61	2.08	57.07	55.22
327	15	0.817	-0.078	0.000	-0.198	100.40	1.70	51.21	49.72
328	15	0.970	-0.078	0.000	-0.203	92.37	1.37	45.71	44.54
329	15	1.124	-0.079	0.000	-0.208	84.52	1.09	40.57	39.66
330	15	1.277	-0.080	0.000	-0.213	76.85	0.86	35.77	35.07

Table 10 (Continued) The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$s_{KM,j,x,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,y,0}$ [m]	$s_{KM,j,z,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
331	15	1.430	-0.081	0.000	-0.218	69.36	0.66	31.29	30.77
332	15	1.583	-0.082	0.000	-0.223	62.04	0.50	27.11	26.75
333	15	1.736	-0.084	0.000	-0.228	54.90	0.36	23.24	22.99
334	15	1.890	-0.087	0.000	-0.233	47.95	0.26	19.64	19.48
335	15	2.043	-0.090	0.000	-0.239	41.17	0.18	16.31	16.21
336	15	2.196	-0.095	0.000	-0.244	34.57	0.12	13.23	13.18
337	15	2.349	-0.103	0.000	-0.249	28.15	0.08	10.39	10.37
338	15	2.503	-0.114	0.000	-0.255	21.90	0.05	7.77	7.77
339	15	2.656	-0.135	0.000	-0.261	15.84	0.03	5.36	5.37
340	15	2.809	-0.162	0.000	-0.267	10.10	0.01	3.22	3.23
341	15	2.962	-0.169	0.000	-0.274	4.93	0.01	1.51	1.51
342	15	3.115	-0.131	0.000	-0.281	0.98	0.00	0.30	0.30

Fig. 3 The GNBA beams and the lumped masses of the OEW mass configuration.

Fig. 4 The GNBA beams and the lumped masses of the DW mass configuration.

IV. Data for the Aerodynamic Model

The planform and the airfoil sections of the GNBA wing were determined in a multi-objective, multidisciplinary optimization (MDO) process, which took into account aerodynamic, weight, and wing main box volume criteria. The aircraft was assumed rigid in the optimization process, without quasi-static aeroelastic corrections applied. More details on the optimization procedures can be found in Appendix E of Ref. [1].

Table 11 summarizes the main geometric parameters of the GNBA. In Table 11, the equivalent wing is a trapezoidal wing with the same exposed area as the true wing, the same straight leading edge, the same span, and the same tip chord. The exposed true wing has its root at $y_r = 1.850$ m, its only trailing edge crank at $y_{ck} = 5.651$ m, and its tip at $y_t = 16.378$ m with respect to the aircraft geometric symmetry plane at $y_0 = 0$. Important properties related to the wing are summarized in Table 12.

Table 11 The main geometric properties of the GNBA.

Symbol	Description	Value	Unit
S	Equivalent wing reference area	116.0	m ²
$\mathcal{R}$	Equivalent wing aspect ratio	9.25	-
λ	Equivalent wing taper ratio	0.315	-
$\bar{c}$	Equivalent wing m.a.c.	3.862	m
b	Wing span	32.756	m
Λ_0	Wing leading edge sweepback angle	30.00	deg
$\Lambda_{1/4}$	Equivalent wing quarter-chord sweepback angle	27.52	deg
S_h	Horizontal tail reference area	25.03	m ²
$\mathcal{R}_h$	Horizontal tail aspect ratio	5.5	-
S_v	Vertical tail reference area	20.49	m ²
$\mathcal{R}_v$	Vertical tail aspect ratio	1.7	-
L_f	Fuselage length	39.15	m
d_f	Fuselage maximum diameter	3.7	m

Table 12 The main geometric properties of the GNBA equivalent and true wings.

Symbol	Description	Value	Unit
S	Equivalent wing reference area	116.0	m ²
S_{exp}	Exposed wing planform area	96.84	m ²
$\mathcal{R}$	Equivalent wing aspect ratio	9.25	-
λ	Equivalent wing taper ratio	0.315	-
$\bar{c}$	Mean aerodynamic chord (m.a.c.)	3.862	m
b	Wing span	32.756	m
Λ_0	Wing leading edge sweepback angle	30.00	deg
$\Lambda_{1/4}$	Equivalent wing quarter-chord sweepback angle	27.52	deg
$\Lambda_{1/2}$	Equivalent wing half-chord sweepback angle	24.93	deg
y_0	Position of aircraft geometric symmetry plane	0.000	m
y_r	True wing root y coordinate	1.850	m
y_{ck}	True wing crank y coordinate	5.651	m
y_t	True wing tip y coordinate	16.378	m
c_r	True wing root chord	6.030	m
c_{ck}	True wing crank chord	3.836	m
c_t	True wing tip chord	1.697	m
$y_{\text{m.a.c.}}$	m.a.c. y coordinate	6.767	m
$\Delta x_{1/4}$	Chordwise distance between the equivalent wing apex and the quarter of the m.a.c.	4.872	m
x_{apex}	Chordwise position of the equivalent wing apex with respect to the fuselage nose	13.440	m
$x_{\text{le,m.a.c.}}$	Chordwise position of the wing m.a.c. leading edge with respect to the fuselage nose	17.347	m
$\Gamma_{r-\text{ck}}$	Mean dihedral angle from root to crank	7.0	deg
$\Gamma_{\text{ck}-t}$	Mean dihedral angle from crank to tip	4.5	deg
c_0	Equivalent wing chord at the geometric symmetry plane	5.386	m
$c_{r,e}$	Equivalent wing root chord	4.969	m
i_w	Built-in wing root airfoil incidence	3.0	deg
i_{ck}	Built-in wing crank airfoil incidence	1.6	deg
i_t	Built-in wing tip airfoil incidence	-2.0	deg
$\bar{t}_r$	Wing root airfoil thickness ratio	0.16	-
$\bar{t}_{\text{ck}}$	Wing crank airfoil thickness ratio	0.11	-
$\bar{t}_t$	Wing tip airfoil thickness ratio	0.10	-

The wing airfoils' relative thickness distribution, $\bar{t}(\bar{x})$, and dimensionless camber line coordinate, $\bar{z}_{\text{cl}}(\bar{x})$, as functions of the dimensionless chordwise coordinate, $0 \leq \bar{x} \leq 1$ (with $\bar{x} = 0$ at the leading edge and $\bar{x} = 1$ at the trailing edge) are

given by the expressions:

$$\bar{t}(\bar{x}) = a_{1/2}\sqrt{\bar{x}} + \sum_{i=1}^4 a_i \bar{x}^i \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{z}_{cl}(\bar{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^6 b_i \bar{x}^i \quad (6)$$

so that the dimensionless coordinates of the airfoil upper ($\bar{z}_u$) and lower ($\bar{z}_l$) contours can be calculated as follows:

$$\bar{z}_u = \bar{z}_{cl} + \frac{1}{2}\bar{t} \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{z}_l = \bar{z}_{cl} - \frac{1}{2}\bar{t} \quad (8)$$

The functions describing the wing root, crank, and tip airfoils are then provided in Table 13. The corresponding geometries are depicted in Fig. 5.

Table 13 Functions describing the thickness and camber lines of the wing airfoils.

Section	Dimensionless thickness and camber functions
Root	$\bar{t}(\bar{x}) = 0.4934\sqrt{\bar{x}} - 0.3649\bar{x} + 0.2149\bar{x}^2 - 0.9325\bar{x}^3 + 0.5931\bar{x}^4$ $\bar{z}_{cl}(\bar{x}) = 0.1484\bar{x} - 1.400\bar{x}^2 + 5.109\bar{x}^3 - 9.031\bar{x}^4 + 7.734\bar{x}^5 - 2.560\bar{x}^6$
Crank	$\bar{t}(\bar{x}) = 0.3813\sqrt{\bar{x}} - 0.4565\bar{x} + 0.6972\bar{x}^2 - 1.159\bar{x}^3 + 0.5431\bar{x}^4$ $\bar{z}_{cl}(\bar{x}) = -0.1047\bar{x} + 1.133\bar{x}^2 - 4.300\bar{x}^3 + 7.833\bar{x}^4 - 6.598\bar{x}^5 + 2.037\bar{x}^6$
Tip	$\bar{t}(\bar{x}) = 0.2535\sqrt{\bar{x}} - 0.06668\bar{x} - 0.1926\bar{x}^2 - 0.1210\bar{x}^3 + 0.1415\bar{x}^4$ $\bar{z}_{cl}(\bar{x}) = 0.05236\bar{x} - 0.4118\bar{x}^2 + 1.457\bar{x}^3 - 2.139\bar{x}^4 + 1.501\bar{x}^5 - 0.4599\bar{x}^6$

The fuselage is comprised of circular cross sections throughout its length, with maximum diameter of 3.7 m. The fuselage contour in the geometric symmetry plane is shown in Fig. 6.

The engine pylons are located at $y = \pm 5.051$ m from the plane of symmetry. The engines' individual thrusts are considered to be applied at such a y coordinate, at 1.975 m below the fuselage center line, and at 13.408 m in the x direction from the fuselage nose. Each engine is assumed to have a toe-in angle of 1.5 deg, together with an incidence of 2.0 deg, both of which affect the individual thrust directions. More details regarding the engines are given in Sec. V.

The isometric and the three orthogonal views of the GNBA were shown in Fig. 1, in which the nacelles were created as bodies of revolution with variable radius in each direction (the horizontal projection maximum diameter is 2.396 m, whereas the vertical projection maximum diameter is 2.040 m). The two-dimensional drawings of their contours were obtained from pictures of similar airplanes and, since they only have aesthetic impact in this work, details about these drawings are omitted for brevity. The pylons are simple airfoil sections connecting the nacelles to the wings, only with aesthetic purposes. The wing-fuselage fairing was created by increasing the fuselage contour radial coordinates near the wing, also based on pictures of similar airplanes.

Fig. 5 The GNBA wing root, crank, and tip airfoils.

Fig. 6 The GNBA fuselage contour in the geometric plane of symmetry.

The horizontal and the vertical tails are trapezoidal, having no cranks in their planforms. The horizontal tail geometric parameters are listed in Table 14, whereas those of the vertical tail are listed in Table 15. In both tables, the reference $z = 0$ for the z coordinates is the center line of the cylindrical portion of the fuselage, as plotted in Fig. 6.

Table 14 The main geometric properties of the GNBA horizontal tail.

Symbol	Description	Value	Unit
S_h	Horizontal tail planform area	25.03	m ²
$\mathcal{R}_h$	Horizontal tail aspect ratio	5.5	-
λ_h	Horizontal tail taper ratio	0.28	-
$\bar{c}_h$	Horizontal tail m.a.c.	2.358	m
b_h	Horizontal tail span	11.733	m
$\Lambda_{0,h}$	Leading edge sweepback angle	33.00	deg
$\Lambda_{1/4,h}$	Quarter-chord sweepback angle	28.68	deg
$z_{0,h}$	Horizontal tail symmetry plane z coordinate	0.912	m
$y_{0,h}$	Horizontal tail symmetry plane y coordinate	0.000	m
$y_{t,h}$	Horizontal tail tip y coordinate	5.866	m
$c_{0,h}$	Horizontal tail chord at the geometric symmetry plane	3.333	m
$c_{t,h}$	Horizontal tail tip chord	0.933	m
$y_{m.a.c.,h}$	Horizontal tail m.a.c. y coordinate	2.383	m
$\Delta x_{1/4,h}$	Chordwise distance between the horizontal tail apex and the quarter of the m.a.c.	2.137	m
$x_{apex,h}$	Chordwise position of the horizontal tail apex with respect to the fuselage nose	34.817	m
$x_{le,m.a.c.,h}$	Chordwise position of the horizontal tail m.a.c. leading edge with respect to the fuselage nose	36.365	m
Γ_h	Mean dihedral angle	7.0	deg
$\bar{t}_h$	Horizontal tail constant airfoil thickness ratio	0.11	-

Table 15 The main geometric properties of the GNBA vertical tail.

Symbol	Description	Value	Unit
S_v	Vertical tail planform area	20.49	m ²
$\mathcal{R}_v$	Vertical tail aspect ratio	1.7	-
λ_v	Vertical tail taper ratio	0.33	-
$\bar{c}_v$	Vertical tail m.a.c.	3.765	m
b_v	Vertical tail span (root to tip)	5.902	m
$\Lambda_{0,v}$	Leading edge sweepback angle	39.00	deg
$\Lambda_{1/4,v}$	Quarter-chord sweepback angle	36.34	deg
$z_{r,v}$	Vertical tail root z coordinate	1.598	m
$z_{t,v}$	Vertical tail tip z coordinate	7.500	m
$c_{r,v}$	Vertical tail root chord	5.221	m
$c_{t,v}$	Vertical tail tip chord	1.723	m
$z_{m.a.c.,v}$	Vertical tail m.a.c. z coordinate	4.053	m
$\Delta x_{1/4,v}$	Chordwise distance between the vertical tail apex and the quarter of the m.a.c.	2.930	m
$x_{apex,v}$	Chordwise position of the vertical tail apex with respect to the fuselage nose	32.850	m
$x_{le,m.a.c.,v}$	Chordwise position of the vertical tail m.a.c. leading edge with respect to the fuselage nose	34.838	m
$\bar{t}_v$	Vertical tail constant airfoil thickness ratio	0.12	-

A. Control Surfaces

The GNBA has an all-moving horizontal tail. Its incidence is represented by i_h and is positive following the right-hand rule about the hinge line that coincides in direction and sense with the aircraft axis y , with the hinge point located at $x = x_{\text{apex,h}} + \Delta x_{1/4,h} = 36.954$ m and $z = 0.984$ m – considering the coordinate system of Fig. 1.

The ailerons can be deflected independently and are located in the wing for $12.775 \leq |y| \leq 15.978$ m, with their leading edges and hinge lines straight and coincident, located at fractions of the chord of 0.7886 at the outboard edge and 0.7361 at the inboard edge. The left aileron deflection is δ_{la} and is positive trailing edge down. The right aileron deflection is δ_{ra} and is also positive trailing edge down.

The elevators can be deflected independently and are located in the horizontal tail for $0.587 \leq |y| \leq 5.866$ m, with their leading edges and hinge lines straight and coincident, located at fractions of the chord of 0.7571 at the outboard edge and 0.6969 at the inboard edge. The left elevator deflection is δ_{le} and is positive trailing edge down. The right elevator deflection is δ_{re} and is also positive trailing edge down.

Lastly, the rudder is located in the vertical tail for $1.850 \leq |z| \leq 7.500$ m, with its leading edge and hinge line straight and coincident, located at fractions of the chord of 0.6861 at the outboard edge and 0.7096 at the inboard edge. The rudder deflection is δ_r and is positive trailing edge to the left (in a top view).

B. Aerodynamic Parasite Drag Model

Whereas the induced drag of the flexible aircraft is more coherently calculated in each time step of a flight simulation considering the instant aircraft deformation, the parasite drag is more conveniently obtained from lookup tables considering the undeformed aircraft. This is obviously a simplification, but the common semi-empirical models available for the estimation of parasite drag are not able to capture the effects of airframe deformation.

The parasite drag contains not only the profile drags of the lifting surfaces – wing, horizontal tail, and vertical tail –, but also the friction and pressure drag of the fuselage, engine nacelles, and pylons, and the wave drag of the wing.

The GNBA parasite drag coefficient is calculated as a function of three independent variables: Mach number (Ma), altitude above sea level (h), and angle of attack (α). Mach number and altitude affect the Reynolds number (Re) according to the International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) model. No dependence of the profile drags of the lifting surfaces is considered with respect to the angle of attack or to the sideslip angle. This explains why the aircraft parasite drag does not depend on the sideslip angle. On the other hand, the aircraft angle of attack affects the fuselage drag and the wing wave drag.

The fuselage parasite drag is calculated based on the methodology of Sec. 4.3 of Ref. [2]. The drag increment due to the rear fuselage upsweep is calculated using Ref. [3].

The wing zero-lift drag is calculated with the methodology of Sec. 4.2.1.1 of Ref. [2]. The wing wave drag in the transonic regime is calculated based on the work of Gur, Mason, and Schetz [4], combined with a vortex-lattice

method (VLM) model of the aircraft lifting surfaces based on Hedman's VLM formulation [5] that provides the wing lift coefficient distribution along the span.

The horizontal and vertical tails' zero-lift drag is calculated using Sec. 4.4.1.1 of Ref. [2]. The parasite drag of the nacelles and pylons is calculated using Sec. 4.5 of Ref. [2]. The interference drag between the nacelles and the wing is calculated multiplying the nacelles' parasite drag by a factor of 1.3, according to Sec. 12.5.5 of Ref. [6].

Finally, the drag associated with things such as the air conditioning system, various cooling systems, and the many necessary protuberances that exist on an airplane also adds to the parasite drag. Such contributions were classified as miscellaneous drag in Ref. [7] and the estimate of a 1.5% increase in the aircraft parasite drag suggested there is assumed for the GNBA.

V. Propulsive Model

The GNBA has two under-wing-mounted engines. The thrust of each engine, T_1 (left engine) and T_2 (right engine), as a function of the propulsive control, δ_1 (left engine) and δ_2 (right engine), is given by:

$$T_1 = \delta_1 T_{\max} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{n_\rho}, \quad (9)$$

$$T_2 = \delta_2 T_{\max} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{n_\rho}, \quad (10)$$

where $T_{\max} = 100000$ N is the maximum thrust at the sea level density, $\rho_0 = 1.225$ kg/m³, ρ is the current air density, and $n_\rho = 0.8$. The dimensionless throttle settings are such that $0 \leq \delta_1 \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \delta_2 \leq 1$.

The geometric parameters listed in Table 16 are fundamental for the calculation of the propulsive forces, moments, and generalized forces. The following definition is needed:

$$\mathbf{C}_i(\mu) = (1 - \cos \mu) \mathbf{e}_{3,i} \mathbf{e}_{3,i}^T + \cos \mu \mathbf{I}_3 - \sin \mu \widetilde{\mathbf{e}_{3,i}}, \quad (11)$$

where the angle μ is in radians, $\mathbf{e}_{3,i}$ is the i th column of the identity matrix of size 3, $\mathbf{I}_3$, and the skew-symmetric operator $\widetilde{\mathbf{n}}$ is defined in Eq. (2) for a generic vector $\mathbf{n}$. In Table 16, the basic coordinate system in which $\mathbf{s}_{P_1,0}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{P_2,0}$ are written coincides with the system $Sx_0y_0z_0$ defined in Sec. II.

Table 16 Geometric data for the GNBA left and right engines.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Left engine inclination angle	ι_1	2.0	deg
Left engine offset angle	τ_1	1.5	deg
Transformation matrix from the body system to the left engine propulsive system	$\mathbf{C}_{p1/b}$	$\mathbf{C}_2(\iota_1)\mathbf{C}_3(\tau_1)$	–
Thrust action point for the left engine (in the basic coordinate system)	$\mathbf{s}_{P1,0}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -3.0899 \\ -5.0505 \\ -1.9752 \end{bmatrix}$	m
Right engine inclination angle	ι_2	2.0	deg
Right engine offset angle	τ_2	-1.5	deg
Transformation matrix from the body system to the right engine propulsive system	$\mathbf{C}_{p2/b}$	$\mathbf{C}_2(\iota_2)\mathbf{C}_3(\tau_2)$	–
Thrust action point for the right engine (in the basic coordinate system)	$\mathbf{s}_{P2,0}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -3.0899 \\ 5.0505 \\ -1.9752 \end{bmatrix}$	m

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